

1 Accessing interactively the spatio-temporal data-model
2 of an archaeological site through its 3D virtual
3 reconstruction

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6 **Abstract**

7 Information and communication technologies are increasingly used in all ar-
8 chaeological processes. However, archaeologists sometimes consider them as
9 intrusive, too far from the traditional work methodology and even a hin-
10 drance. In this article we propose a framework to allow natural and there-
11 fore intuitive access to the archaeological record. The information retrieval
12 process is carried out through a three-dimensional virtual reconstruction of
13 the archaeological site. In this system, navigation and interaction with the
14 three-dimensional elements of the environment triggers database queries. To
15 achieve such functionality, a client-server architecture is designed in which
16 the server maintains a spatio-temporal database with heterogeneous informa-
17 tion, including the 3D models of the finds. To do this, a virtual replica of the
18 site is created considering spatial restrictions and topological relationships
19 among the finds.

20 *Keywords:* Spatio-temporal database, Virtual 3D archaeological site
21 reconstruction, Topological relationship, 3D navigation and interaction

22 **1. Introduction and state of the art**

23 Many disciplines are contributing with new processes and methods for
24 capturing, registering, analysing and disseminating data in Archaeology. Amid
25 all of them, ICT (Information and Communication Technology) is one of the
26 most relevant, since it can be useful for each of the mentioned phases [1]. Suc-
27 cessfully incorporating ICT techniques in the archaeological workflow can be

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28 a real challenge, since archaeologists have to feel at ease with the new tools,
29 and perceive them as really worth the effort of using them. This also implies
30 that software development for Archaeology should be more user-centered, in
31 order to provide the best user experience possible [2].

32 Considering that the real world is three-dimensional, one of these ad-
33 vances consists of using 3D virtual models in the archaeological workflow.
34 Therefore, in the data acquisition phase, 2D images (photographs or draw-
35 ings) can be replaced by three-dimensional models of the finds. Some ad-
36 vanced techniques such as photogrammetry or laser scanning are increas-
37 ingly used for data capturing [3, 4]. Scanning of finds is a common desire of
38 archaeologists, especially of pieces considered relevant. Although scanning
39 equipment is increasingly portable and affordable, it is not always feasible
40 to obtain 3D models of all the objects found. We find in the literature some
41 approaches focusing on different techniques to facilitate the process [5, 6].
42 In any case, the process is slow, usually carried out in the laboratory with
43 the right lighting conditions, and once the pieces have been cleaned. On
44 the other hand, the amount of data generated by these technologies causes
45 different issues that are not easy to solve [7]. Archaeologists are in charge of
46 analysing and interpreting this information, and sometimes of managing the
47 necessary software tools.

48 Documentation is a common goal of all archaeological processes, thus data
49 acquisition on site is typically followed by an exhaustive review of the infor-
50 mation and feeding of the archaeological record. For this reason, databases
51 play a very important role in storing and organizing this information [8].
52 Data in records usually include varied information such as blueprints, pho-
53 tographs, scans, sketches or alphanumeric information. The way of access-
54 ing this information typically requires a certain level of expertise, especially
55 in the analysis phase when it is necessary to run complex queries on this
56 database. The integration of this workflow is the goal of many research
57 groups [9, 10, 11].

58 Dissemination is an issue in which a significant amount of efforts have
59 been concentrated. There is a great conviction that high detailed 3D virtual
60 models are very useful tools to show ancient places and vestiges to the general
61 public [12]. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) have contributed to the
62 displaying of pieces and archaeological sites, including the 3D reconstruction
63 of the sites [13, 14, 15, 16]. However, the same efforts have not been made to
64 improve the user experience of the software tools for archaeologists. As well
65 as archaeological records should be transformed into more understandable

66 formats for the general public, archaeologists should also be provided with
67 more user-friendly software tools for managing such heterogeneous informa-
68 tion.

69 In short, only a few efforts in the field of 3D graphics are aimed at facil-
70 itating the work of the archaeologists. The recreation of the archaeological
71 site, as well as the excavation process in digital format while keeping the
72 scale, shape and appearance of the objects is a clear goal in this context.
73 Sometimes the archaeologists can feel overwhelmed by technology. Thus,
74 ICT-based methodologies for the capture, documentation and analysis pro-
75 cesses should be rethought, improving the user experience [17]. Software
76 tools must be focused on the virtual recreation of the site conditions in
77 terms of visualization, interaction, and even collaborative analysis, for ex-
78 ample, through a web portal [18]. However, this issue can not be reduced to
79 a mere implementation of a user-friendly interface. An archaeological record
80 is complex and made of heterogeneous data [19]. On the other hand, archae-
81 ological methodologies were defined many decades ago, and fully migrating
82 them into digital form is not a simple task.

83 There are several issues associated with handling 3D archaeological in-
84 formation. One challenge is sharing the 3D representation of an excavation
85 through the Internet [20]. Apart from visualization, 3D models themselves
86 provide poor information, and there is not always a supporting database
87 [21]. 3D models are the result of a digitization process and have to be com-
88 plemented with additional information stored in the digital record. This can
89 make further data query and analysis difficult. Therefore, heterogeneous data
90 such as text fields, photographs, drawings and complex 3D models have to be
91 combined in the documentation process [22]. Developing a software tool ca-
92 pable of grouping all types of heterogeneous data under the same information
93 system is not an easy task. Data has to be displayed with different visualiza-
94 tion tools and thus being analysed separately by experts. This disaggregation
95 of information associated with the archaeological record contributes to the
96 lack of operability from the archaeological point of view.

97 Some of these problems can be solved using Geographic Information Sys-
98 tems (GIS), which provide geospatial storage capabilities [23, 24]. Advances
99 in software and hardware in these platforms can contribute to the visualiza-
100 tion [25], data storage and documentation [26]. Additionally, they also facil-
101 itate the spatial analysis of the individual remains, study the relationships
102 among them, and with the ancient landscape. GIS can store the position
103 of each find in the archaeological site and the layer or stratum where it was

104 located. It is usual to add the UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator) coor-
105 dinates for more accurate positioning [27, 28]. In order to deal with the issue
106 associated with the statement: "excavation is destruction", it is highly rele-
107 vant to keep as much information as possible about the position and spatial
108 distribution of the finds to compensate for this loss [29]. However, GIS is
109 not yet a standard tool for Archaeology, and they are still in the process of
110 integrating 3D with full functionality.

111 One additional issue is that location, as an isolated piece of data, is
112 not enough to establish relationships between one find and its environment.
113 However, these relationships may help the experts discover new information
114 that might go unnoticed during the excavation. Photogrammetric techniques
115 help record the different stages of the excavation by obtaining detailed 3D
116 models at specific moments of the process [5, 6]. However, there is typically
117 a disaggregation between 3D models and the rest of the fields that complete
118 the archaeological record. They are even accessible through different software
119 tools. The process for registering one find considering not only its position,
120 but also its spatial relationships with the rest of the surrounding elements can
121 be performed with a spatial database that supports topological relationships
122 [30]. In this way it is guaranteed that once one piece is extracted, it remains
123 linked to its environment for posterity, just as it was in the past.

124 Topological operators have already been studied in archaeology [31]. The
125 topological model named "Dimensionally Extended Nine-Intersection Model"
126 (DE-9IM) is defined as a 3x3 matrix which determines the spatial relations
127 between two 2D geometries [32]. This matrix can be extended to 3D as a
128 more complex 5x5 matrix or 25-intersection model [33]. Although applying
129 relational operators to each pair of elements to discover their relationships
130 can be enriching, it does not replace the expressiveness that visualization can
131 provide. Therefore, the record must be completed with figurative elements
132 such as images or photographs. Again, the result is still a heterogeneous and
133 decoupled dataset.

134 Thus, software tools aimed at managing 3D archaeological records need
135 the support of a specific data model able to integrate the diversified infor-
136 mation of an archaeological site. An additional differentiating element in
137 this type of 3D environment is the graphical interface to deal with the data.
138 This type of tool generates a virtual scene in which both the remains and
139 their spatial arrangement are recreated. With these tools, excavation does
140 not necessarily imply destruction, but digital reconstruction. A digital copy
141 of the site is obtained for posterity [34]. Therefore, software must go beyond

142 a high resolution visualization of the finds distributed in the same spatial
143 arrangement where they were discovered.

144 Navigation and interaction are two other important issues that have to
145 be addressed. For these purposes, some approaches take advantage of the
146 capabilities of video game engines [13, 35, 36]. Regarding navigation, the
147 virtual reconstruction of an archaeological site allows us to remove irrelevant
148 elements like the soil surrounding the vestiges, and thus enables us to ana-
149 lyze aspects such as the spatial arrangement of the finds. Interaction with
150 the 3D virtual site can become the natural way for accessing the archaeo-
151 logical record. Interaction is already accepted as the most intuitive way to
152 access information [35, 37]. The concept of computer-human interaction is
153 being incorporated as the natural way to access 3D models, sometimes using
154 haptic devices [38]. Clicking on a model can trigger a set of different op-
155 erations, including spatial and non-spatial queries and analysis. This might
156 require a previous stage to separate the virtual vestiges from the surrounding
157 soil and objects applying segmentation techniques [39]. One step further in
158 these processes is enabling access to the 3D environment through an Internet
159 connection, which facilitates experts all over the world to virtually visit the
160 site.

161 Finally, the registration process normally carried out throughout different
162 campaigns, can also be analysed considering its temporal information, not
163 only in relation to history, but detailing the work sequence carried out on site.
164 The spatio-temporal component has traditionally been another important
165 factor when querying and analyzing archaeological information [3, 31, 40].
166 The problem sometimes is the way this information is provided to the re-
167 searchers in terms of usability.

168 In this paper we present a framework in which an archaeological site is
169 virtually recreated with the main objective of facilitating access to the in-
170 formation system. The integrated data model can be managed exclusively
171 through an interactive Graphical User Interface (GUI). The heterogeneous
172 information is maintained in a database with spatio-temporal and topologi-
173 cal capabilities hosted on a server. On the client-side, an application running
174 on a video-game engine provides the user with a 3D graphical interface to
175 visualize and interact with the reconstruction of the archaeological site. The
176 information in the database is accessed through this interface, by interacting
177 in real-time with the elements in the 3D scene. The temporal component of
178 the data is also available for the user using two timelines, one related with
179 the excavation process and the other one related to the historical dating of

180 the finds. The resulting software prototype is aimed at providing a good
181 user experience to the archaeologist, facilitating access to the archaeological
182 records. The client-server architecture allows the expert to access the ar-
183 chaeological site from any place at any time since, contrary to a real site, the
184 3D model remains for posterity.

185 The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 synthesizes the main con-
186 tributions of this work. Section 3 describes the data and the nomenclature
187 used in this framework. Section 4 provides an overview of the system archi-
188 tecture. The spatio-temporal database is described in Section 5 and finally,
189 Section 6 shows how advanced queries to the database can be performed by
190 interacting with the virtual replica of the archaeological site. Conclusions
191 and future work are presented in Section 7.

192 2. Main contribution

193 In this paper, we propose a new methodology focused on the user ex-
194 perience of archaeologists for managing the information of an archaeological
195 excavation. A paradigm shift is proposed to make the mode of accessing
196 such information closer to the archaeological work, and not the other way
197 around. To achieve such an objective, an information system is implemented
198 in which the archaeological site is virtually reconstructed as a digital replica
199 of the site. The way of accessing the archaeological record is directly inter-
200 acting with the 3D Graphical User Interface of the system. The most natural
201 way of accessing a piece is directly through the object itself, by allowing its
202 visualization and manipulation. Taking advantage of the fact that the finds
203 have been digitized and stored in a database, these mechanisms can also be-
204 come virtual. Therefore, accessing the information means to observe strata
205 and findings like the soil around them disappears. In addition, accessing the
206 data stored in the spatial database is performed by simply navigating and
207 clicking on the virtual site. These objects maintain the original spatial ar-
208 rangement in terms of scale, position and orientation. Additional topological
209 and temporal relationships between finds are also configured in the database.
210 The result is an integrated system with database query and analysis capa-
211 bilities that help the archaeological work change the concept of "excavation
212 is destruction" to "excavation is virtual reconstruction".

213 We have designed a spatio-temporal and topological database imple-
214 mented in PostgreSQL using the PostGIS extension. Each element can be
215 stored with different kinds of attributes, including its 3D model. Topological

216 relations can be added to these models to link the elements by their spatial
217 relationship as they were found during the excavation. Moreover, new re-
218 lationships can be suggested automatically, based on topological operators.
219 Advantages of maintaining topology in the database are mainly focused on
220 further analysis. If, for example, two ceramic pieces have been found to-
221 gether, it is very likely that they are parts of the same original recipient, or
222 at least be part of the same set. Any click on a model can provide the set
223 of objects related to it, their appearance and relative position. Even relative
224 distance between each other can be directly obtained. Obviously, these ac-
225 tions generate queries to the topological database. As a response, the system
226 provides the required information, that is shown through the 3D GUI.

227 As part of this analysis is the possibility of keeping the extraction process
228 alive, reliving the state and initial placement of the finds in relation to the
229 rest of the pieces and the environment. In addition to the spatial analysis,
230 the temporal nature of the extraction process can be represented in our data
231 model, allowing the temporal sequencing of the process. In short, a query
232 like: *"list all the objects extracted from the layer <<layer_name>> after the*
233 *date <<yy-mm-dd>> made of material <<material_type>>"* can be easily
234 formed through the interaction with the 3D virtual site.

235 In summary, this paper presents a framework and a system prototype
236 with the following capabilities:

- 237 • The 3D recreation of the archaeological site maintaining scale and spa-
238 tial arrangement.
- 239 • A user-friendly interface to provide access to the information through
240 a virtual 3D replica of the archaeological site.
- 241 • Integration of all the processes in the same platform: capture, data
242 recording, visualization, analysis and dissemination.
- 243 • A topological and spatio-temporal database able to manage heteroge-
244 neous information, including 3D models.
- 245 • Accessible through the Internet for collective and remote analysis.

246 **3. Data description**

247 In this section, we describe the concepts and terminology used in the pa-
248 per associated with an archaeological excavation. We have used data from

Figure 1: Schematic view of the concepts of *Area*, *Volume*, *Layer* and *Element*

249 the excavations in the Iberian-Roman city of Castulo, one of the capital cen-
 250 tres in southern Spain during the Antiquity. Castulo was the most important
 251 population centre in the Iberian Oretania and it later turned into a Roman
 252 city. The archaeological site contains other settlements from the Prehistory
 253 to the Late Middle Ages, which complete the historical value of this ar-
 254 chaeological area. This complex stratigraphic and temporal sequence, which
 255 remains in our time with exceptional integrity and preservation conditions,
 256 constitutes a significant segment of the whole history of Andalusia.

257 Archaeologists working on Castulo use the following concepts to organize
 258 the information from the site (Figure 1 represents the relationships among
 259 several of these concepts).

260 An *Archaeological Site* is a location where archaeologists decide that there
 261 are interesting remains to be explored and discovered through excavation.
 262 The usual way of working on an archaeological site is through excavation
 263 *Campaigns* that have a given start and end date. Each campaign can have
 264 different duration. In order to organize the space in an archaeological site, the
 265 archaeologists define *Areas*. Each area is a closed superficial perimeter that

Figure 2: Aerial view of an archaeological site, with two highlighted areas. Although areas are not 3D, they are drawn here as parallelepipeds, so that they can be seen over the 3D terrain model

266 encloses excavation activities (Figure 2). Inside an area, a variable number of
267 *Volumes* (Figure 3.a) can be defined. A volume not only comprises a closed
268 superficial perimeter, but also the ground below. As the ground from the
269 volume is removed, the archaeologists define *Layers* (Figure 3.b), determined
270 by relevant changes in the ground (different composition, color, materials
271 found, dating of the discoveries, etcetera).

272 Finally, the materials found during the excavation of each layer can be
273 of different natures: pottery, bones, buildings, statues, etc. In our database
274 structure, we have used the more general term *Element* to group all these
275 findings, and then allow a unified treatment of the information (Figure 4).

276 4. System overview

277 Figure 5 shows the system architecture of the client-server prototype. The
278 archaeological records containing all the information are stored in a spatial
279 database hosted on the server side. On the client-side, a user application
280 implemented in Unity, allows full access to this information through the 3D
281 virtual recreation of the site.

282 4.1. Server side

283 As Figure 5 shows, the server maintains a database in PostGIS, an ex-
284 tension for PostgreSQL that supports geometric and geographic data types
285 and their operations. The database is fed with the information obtained
286 in the acquisition phase, which can be performed with traditional or new

Figure 3: a) Two volumes defined inside an area. Each volume is composed of a series of layers (b), in which the elements are located (red dots)

Figure 4: View of the elements inside a given layer

Figure 5: General scheme of the system and technologies used

287 methodologies. The more complete the acquisition process, the more analyt-
288 ical capacity the future system will have. In this paper we are not focusing
289 on this facet of the system but on the interactive access to the data.

290 The connection between the database and the user application is per-
291 formed by means of a REST (Representational State Transfer) API, as de-
292 picted in the same figure. This Application Program Interface is a stateless
293 client-server protocol based on HTTP requests that contain all the required
294 information when data is transferred between origin and destination. This
295 protocol allows a fluid communication between client and server to perform
296 operations of data querying, insertion, deletion or update without the need
297 for external libraries. The server hosts the REST API and receives requests
298 using the JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) data exchange format; then,
299 the server interprets, processes and sends back data to the client in the same
300 format. The advantage of the REST protocol is the separation between the
301 user interface and the data storage system. This improves the portability of
302 the interface as well as increases the scalability of the project, allowing their
303 different components to evolve independently.

304 *4.2. The client application*

305 Once the database has been fed, including the 3D models of the finds,
306 the analysis phase can start on the client side. For that purpose, any device
307 connected to the Internet and with certain graphic capabilities can be used.
308 As stated above, this application is implemented in Unity, a cross-platform
309 real-time video game engine with 3D visualization and interaction capabil-
310 ities. This virtual scenario is presented to the user as the natural way of
311 accessing the information stored in the archaeological database. This means
312 an easy browse based on the virtual replica of findings instead of writing
313 complex queries using languages like SQL.

314 Figure 6 shows the user interface of the application. It normally visualizes
315 any of the entities described in Figure 1. In this example, the elements of a
316 specific layer are observed, together with their topological relationships. In
317 the scene, the user can freely navigate and interact with the objects using the
318 mouse or any Virtual Reality device by taking advantage of the Unity game
319 engine capabilities. The figure highlights the application main screen and its
320 controls. Selecting specific layers or volumes can be performed by directly
321 writing them on the text box attribute filtering (6.(1)), or by navigating in
322 the hierarchy of screens (Figures 2 and 3). Some additional controls such

Figure 6: Main screen of the application. (1): attribute filtering options. (2): switch for enabling/disabling the visualization of the digital elevation model of the terrain and refresh view control. (3): control to browse back in the data model. (4): breadcrumb trail and time slider. (5): shows/hides a table with the data in the current view.

Figure 7: Overview of the whole structure of the database. Figures 8 to 16 focus on each block

323 as the one of Figure 6.(4) facilitates temporary queries. Section 6 describes
 324 some use cases comparing this interactive method and the SQL queries.

325 5. Database

326 Our interface proposal is supported by a database that includes not only
 327 the typical record information related to each find (id, name, material, type of
 328 object, etcetera) that can be seen in similar proposals, but also the informa-
 329 tion related to locations, topology and dating. Figure 7 shows a general view
 330 of the database structure that we have defined. We are going to summarize
 331 the main characteristics of our design in the following subsections.

332 5.1. Main entities

333 Figure 8 shows the table structure chosen to store the basic information
 334 about the excavation structure and the findings. The table structure and
 335 relationships match the description from Section 3.

336 For each find (*Element*), apart from its 3D model, we store a transfor-
 337 mation matrix (to place that 3D model in the virtual reconstruction of the

Figure 8: Entities defined to store the basic information about the archaeological site

Figure 9: Materials representation

338 site) and the projections of that 3D model into the Euclidean planes XY, XZ
 339 and YZ. These projections are necessary in order to compute the DE-9IM
 340 matrices between each pair of finds that are close enough. These projections
 341 are computed only once when the 3D models are inserted in the database.
 342 Apart from that, a JSON attribute is included in this entity, so that any
 343 additional information not considered in the design can be added. This in-
 344 formation can be easily handled with the PostgreSQL JSON functions and
 345 operators, therefore enriching the expressiveness of the model.

346 5.2. Materials

347 The information related to the material each finding is made of is quite
 348 simple, as we are not focused on this topic. We simply have one entity with

Figure 10: Image storage system

349 the name of the material and a description (Figure 9).

350 5.3. Images

351 Instead of storing the images inside the database as binary information,
 352 we decided to store them in an external storage, and keep in the database
 353 just the URL to find them (Figure 10). Images are directly linked to either
 354 an element (a finding) or a layer. The client application offers the possibility
 355 of showing the images related to a find near its 3D model; for this purpose,
 356 the orientation (*direction*) and distance from the 3D model where the image
 357 is to be placed are also stored.

358 5.4. Users

359 User accounts do not require any special treatment. The typical informa-
 360 tion for allowing user identification is complemented by a set of permissions
 361 to operate on the information stored in the database. As the users are allowed
 362 to add comments to the finds (*elements*), this information is also stored in
 363 the database (Figure 11).

364 5.5. Coordinates

365 The two most relevant features of our proposal are related to the spatial
 366 and the temporal information. In order to provide a successful and friendly
 367 interface to the users, we opted not to restrict the spatial representation
 368 to a single coordinate system, but to offer the possibility of storing each
 369 coordinate using either the UTM or the WGS84 reference system (Figure
 370 12). Conversions are performed as necessary during the calculations required

Figure 11: Tables to store the user information and their comments

Figure 12: Data representation for spatial coordinates

Figure 13: Entities for storing historical data information

371 for data visualization or any other spatial query, since UTM is our preferred
 372 reference system, but internally, the original information is kept as it was
 373 inserted by the users.

374 5.6. Dating system

375 We keep track of two different dating information: the historical (Figure
 376 13) and the excavation dating, which usually is the date of insertion in the
 377 database (Figure 14). We do so in order to allow the possibility of using the
 378 GUI of our application to review the findings in sequence either according to
 379 the date they were discovered, or according to the dating the archaeologists
 380 assign to them.

381 Regarding excavation dating, every new insertion of areas, volumes, layers
 382 and elements also includes a new tuple in the *EntryInfo* table, in order to
 383 keep track of the excavation chronology. These dates are also linked to a
 384 *Campaign*, as described in Section 3. This allows us to browse through
 385 the evolution of the excavation, in order to provide further evidence for the
 386 analysis of the discoveries.

Figure 14: Entities for storing excavation dating information

387 Partly inspired by the work by Belussi and Migliorini [31], the historical
 388 dating system considers two different possibilities to assign a date to a dis-
 389 covery. For those cases in which the date is clear (for example: a tombstone
 390 with the date of the death), a *CalendarDate* can be assigned. However, most
 391 of the time the exact dating of each finding is not clear. Therefore, we also
 392 allow assigning an *EraDate* to the finding. Each *Era* can have a starting and
 393 an ending date, more or less accurate (day, month and year, only year, or
 394 month and year).

395 5.7. Topology

396 In this context, topological relationships describe how finds are connected
 397 in the site under the premise "if two objects are close together in the site,
 398 they could have been related in antiquity". This premise may not be true,
 399 but it provides the archaeologist with a catalog of possible related pieces with
 400 additional information such as the type of the possible topological relation
 401 (disjoint, meet, overlap, contained, etc.), as well as the distance between the
 402 pieces (in the case of disjoint).

403 The standard to describe spatial relations in 2D is the Dimensionally Ex-
 404 tended 9-Intersection Model (DE-9IM) [32, 41], which determines how two
 405 objects are spatially connected, no matter their rotation, translation and
 406 scaling transformations. The DE-9IM model is really useful for 2D geomet-
 407 rical models, but it can not be applied to 3D models straightforwardly. Due
 408 to the fact that the 3D version, called DE-25IM [33], is not available in Post-

Figure 15: Projection of an amphora fragment into the three orthogonal planes

Figure 16: Entity used to store topological information

409 GIS, we propose another solution based on DE-9IM. In this approach, we
410 compute the 2D projections of the original 3D geometries on each of the
411 three orthogonal planes: XY, YZ and XZ (Figure 15). Then, for each pair of
412 pieces that are close enough, according to a distance threshold that can be
413 chosen by the user, the DE-9IM matrices computed from their projections
414 are obtained and stored in the database (Figure 16).

415 In order to find close elements, the PostGIS function *ST_Buffer* is used to
416 create influence buffers using the distance threshold for each 2D projection;
417 then, these 2D influence buffers are checked for intersection with the function
418 *ST_Intersects*. For each pair of elements whose buffers intersect, the DE-
419 9IM matrix of their projections is computed and stored using the function
420 *ST_Relate*.

421 The fact that there is an intersection between the projections in 2D does
422 not necessarily mean that the objects intersect in 3D. However, this allows
423 the expert to do a massive filtering of pieces that for spatial reasons are not
424 likely to have a relationship.

425 6. Data analysis

426 One of the biggest challenges in the application of ICT to archaeological
427 recording is providing archaeologists with a user-friendly method to browse
428 through the recorded data. The amount of records obtained in a typical
429 excavation campaign is usually very high, and successive campaigns on the
430 same site continue increasing this number. In the end, trying to locate a given
431 record can become an arduous task, even through running SQL standard
432 queries.

433 In order to prove the usefulness of our system proposal, in this section
434 we are going to show two example queries on our database, comparing them
435 with the steps in our client 3D application for obtaining the same result. The
436 biggest advantage is that no SQL knowledge is required for creating really
437 complex queries.

438 6.1. Example 1

439 Consider the following query: *show all the pottery pieces from the Roman*
440 *Age that were found between June 6th, 2020 and June 7th, 2020 in layer 410,*
441 *together with the pieces that are likely to be related to them.* Implementing
442 this query in SQL results in a code as complex as the following:

```

443 select e.id, e.elements_related related,
444         trim(m.type_material) material, trim(era.name) era,
445         ei.date date
446 from public."Element" e
447 inner join public."Material" m on e.material_id = m.id
448 inner join public."EraDate" ed on e.id = ed.element_id
449 inner join public."Era" era on era.id = ed.era_id
450 inner join public."EntryInfo" ei on e.entry_info_id = ei.id
451 where e.layer_id = 410 and m.type_material = 'Ceramics' and
452        era.name = 'Roman age' and
453        ( ei.date >= '2020-06-06 00:00:00' and
454          ei.date <= '2020-06-07 23:59:59')
455 order by e.id;

```

456 With our client-side 3D application, the steps to achieve the same result
457 are the following:

- 458 1. From the initial view, browse to layer 410 (click on the area, then on
459 the volume and then on the layer).
- 460 2. Use the attribute filter to choose “material”, choose operator “equal
461 to” and write “ceramics”.
- 462 3. Use the “historical era” filter to choose “Roman Age”.
- 463 4. Use the “excavation dating” filter to restrict the range to the dates
464 June 6th, 2020 - June 7th, 2020.

465 The result of following these steps is shown on Figure 17. Red lines link
466 the pieces that are considered as related, according to the information in the
467 database.

468 6.2. Example 2

469 Consider the following query: *show all the pieces from layer 410 dated in*
470 *1310, with identification number less than 3125 and that were found on June*
471 *1st 2020.* Trying to obtain this information from the database using SQL
472 results in a piece of code similar to this:

```

473 select e.id, make_date(cd.year, lower(cd.month),
474                      lower(cd.day)) as min_date,
475        make_date(cd.year, upper(cd.month)-1, upper(cd.day)-1) max_date,
476        ei.date

```


Figure 17: Result of one query using our client-side 3D application. Numbers in red identify 1- Attribute filter (in this example, it is set to “material = ceramics”). 2- Historical era filter (in this example, it is set to “Roman Age”). 3- Breadcrumbs to help the researcher know what they are browsing, excavation date filter (in this example, it is set to the interval [2020/06/06, 2020/06/07]) and historical dating filter.

```

477 from public."Element" e, public."CalendarDate" cd,
478     public."EntryInfo" ei
479 where e.id = cd.element_id and e.entry_info_id = ei.id and
480        e.layer_id = 410 and e.id < 3125 and cd.year = 1310 and
481        ( ei.date >= '01-06-2020 00:00:00' and
482          ei.date <= '01-06-2020 23:59:59' )
483 order by e.id;

```

484 However, obtaining this information interactively with our client-side ap-
485 plication is as simple as following these steps:

- 486 1. From the initial view, browse to layer 410 (click on the area, then on
487 the volume and then on the layer).
- 488 2. Use the attribute filter to choose “id”, choose operator “less than”, and
489 write 3125.
- 490 3. Use the “historical dating” filter to set the interval to the year 1310.
- 491 4. Use the “excavation date” filter to set the interval [2020/06/01, 2020/06/01].

492 The result is shown on Figure 18.

Figure 18: Result of one query using our client-side 3D application. Numbers in red identify 1- Attribute filter (in this example, it is set to “id < 3125”). 2- Breadcrumbs to help the researcher know what they are browsing, excavation date filter (in this example, it is set to the interval [2020/06/01, 2020/06/01]) and historical dating filter (in this example, it is set to year 1310).

493 7. Conclusions and future work

494 This paper introduces a prototype of an information system with spatial,
 495 topological and temporal features for archaeological recording. The main
 496 objective of this work is providing intuitive access to the archaeological in-
 497 formation through a graphical 3D user interface. This allows querying the
 498 database by means of navigating in the virtual scenario and interacting with
 499 the models of the finds. The process is therefore similar to being present on
 500 the site, since the user works with a replica of the place, both in the modeling
 501 of the pieces and in their spatial arrangement.

502 The paper describes both the spatio-temporal database structure and the
 503 system architecture. It also describes how complex SQL queries that are nor-
 504 mally necessary to extract spatio-temporal information can be replaced by
 505 intuitive interactions to access the information through the 3D representa-
 506 tion of the archaeological site. The system proposes spatial and topological
 507 relationships that a human expert has to confirm or discard. This means of
 508 accessing the database provides a powerful tool to support researchers that
 509 have to deal with the massive amount of data that can be produced in a

510 typical archaeological excavation.

511 Future work is focused on the application of these techniques in a real
512 archaeological site. The best sites to be applied is in new excavations, in
513 which recording and analysis methodologies can be put into operation from
514 the beginning. Although we do not currently have access to any site that
515 meets this requirement, we do expect to implement it in one that is already
516 in progress. Archaeologists from the University of Jaén are working in the
517 Santo Domingo Convent (Jaén), currently not in religious use and managed
518 by the city council. In previous campaigns, very diverse vestiges have been
519 found, including the remains of a plasterwork arcade of Almohad period that
520 would be dated in the XII-XIII century. Findings from the Christian era were
521 also discovered in upper strata. The excavation process has not concluded,
522 and we are ready to start working using the proposed methodology from this
523 moment on. Regarding previous campaigns, the excavation team carried out
524 a traditional recording process, including several scans of the strata. With
525 these data, the photographs of the site and the access to the remains, we do
526 not guarantee perfect replication, but it may mean an improvement in the
527 way of accessing the information already acquired.

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